

Exploring the contribution of decolonisation epistemologies: Promoting social justice in accounting education

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With many countries across the globe failing to deliver an education system that works for and favours all their citizens, calls for mother tongue instruction have intensified. This qualitative study explored the perceived contribution of decolonisation epistemologies in promoting social justice and language equity in accounting education. Positioned in the epistemological assumptions of the critical theory of education and interpretivism, data were collected from a sample of eighteen accounting educators using focus group interviews and a questionnaire for triangulation purposes. The main findings underscore the perceived importance of mother tongue instruction in promoting social justice and language equity in accounting education and yet question the feasibility, sustainability, and practicability of mother tongue instruction. Responding to these polarised findings, this study recommends extensive consultations between custodians of education systems and language experts in collaboration with subject content experts together with well-articulated pilot projects. The paper further cautions that in the absence of plausible supporting scientific evidence, mother tongue instruction threatens to reverse the gains of social cohesion and the global village delivered by a common language of instruction across the globe.

Keywords: Accounting Education; Decolonisation Epistemologies; Language Equity; Mother Tongue Instruction; Social Justice

1. Introduction

Just like decolonisation epistemologies themselves, (Dawson, 2020; Horsthemke, 2017; Jansen, 2017; Letsekha, 2022; Manathunga et al., 2021; Mahabeer, 2021; Mdzanga & Moeng, 2021; R'boul, 2022; Sibanda, 2019), the call for mother tongue instruction across the curriculum to promote social justice and language equity in education remains a highly contested and polarised phenomenon both in the national and global educational spaces (Lumadi, 2021; Liu, 2020; Qi et al., 2021). Owing to these robust discourses on issues of equal access to higher education and the demands of decolonisation epistemologies, the higher education environment is always a fiercely contested and politicized space. Among these debates is the recognition and

adoption of indigenous and Afrocentric epistemologies and ontologies in teaching, learning, research, and scholarly engagements. To achieve this, the advocates of a decolonized education are advocating for the use of mother tongue as a legitimate and official language of instruction across the curriculum.

Research demonstrates that the custodians of education are unanimous on the importance of mother tongue instruction across the curriculum in promoting and advancing social justice and language equity in education (Letsekha, 2022; Lumadi, 2021; Nyika, 2015; Sibanda, 2019). Evidence from literature confirms that support for mother tongue instruction has been registered in many countries across the globe such as Canada, Tanzania, South Africa, Sweden, Australia, Germany, Australia, and Iran (Eisenclas et al., 2013; Ganuza & Hedman, 2017; Oral & Lund, 2022; Salmani Nodoushan, 2016; Sibanda, 2019). While literature seems to be very silent on the feasibility, sustainability and practicability of mother tongue instruction, there are studies which show that mother tongue instruction can positively affect academic performance (Nyika 2015; Sibanda, 2019). Evidence to substantiate this claim is found in a previous study by Eloff (2017) in which learners who accessed the curriculum through mother tongue instruction demonstrated a more than 30% higher pass rate than their counterparts who were taught in a second language. Supporting the above, Eloff (2017) submits that a report on the 'Progress in International Reading Literacy Study' (PIRLS) demonstrated that learners with the best results had written the test in their home language. Even in higher education, Nyika (2015) attributes the failure of many students in developing countries to the use of a second language as the legitimate language of instruction. For Nyika (2015) many universities in Africa have adopted and institutionalised colonial languages as the official language of instruction, thereby creating a barrier for second language students.

This study explored the contribution of decolonization epistemologies¹ in promoting social justice and language equity in accounting education. To corroborate and interrogate the theoretical verdicts from relevant literature on decolonization epistemologies, the study went further to obtain the perceptions of accounting educators on the feasibility, sustainability, and practicability of mother tongue instruction in accounting education. This was also aimed at addressing the concerns of scholars such as R'boul (2022), Walker (2020) and Lumadi (2021), whose views seem to suggest that the discourse on decolonial epistemologies is theoretically limited. Following a qualitative approach, data was collected using open ended questions in questionnaires and follow up focus group interviews. There is a very strong concurrence between literature perspectives and the study participants on the contribution of decolonization epistemologies in promoting social justice and language equity in higher education. Furthermore, the need to transform

higher education through policy reforms and pedagogical practices has been well underscored and flagged, both in literature perspectives and by the study participants (Nyika, 2015; Sibanda, 2019). However, the accounting educators who participated in this study raised some serious concerns about the feasibility, sustainability, and practicability of mother tongue instruction as a call to decolonize the curriculum and accounting education in particular. Similar findings have also been registered in previous studies by Liu (2020) and Nyika (2015).

2. Background

Since meaning is often injected into any utterance from outside (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2022), it is important to unpack the concept of mother tongue instruction and its implied meaning—especially in the context of a multilingual country like South Africa in which this study was conducted—and how it is perceived differently globally. In these multilingual contexts, concepts such as home language, mother tongue, and first language have been used invariably to convey different meanings (Eisenclas et al., 2013; Nyika, 2015; Oral & Lund, 2022; Sibanda, 2019). Oral and Lund, (2022) argue that mother tongue instruction is not only about a school and academic performance idea, but it reflects identity and carries a sense of being, all of which are informed by political forces. Oral and Lund, (2022) concur with Ganuza and Hedman's (2017) view of mother tongue as a language which is spoken by the student's guardian or parents. However, this perception is disputed by Eisenclas et al. (2013), who believe that this view refers to home language. Thus, Eisenclas et al.'s (2013) definition of home language is a language which is predominantly spoken in the student's household. Nyika (2015) supports this view and adds that home language is the language which is spoken in the area where an individual originates from, stays in, or is fluent in. However, all of these views can be contested, depending on the school of thought which one subscribes to.

Ganuza and Hedman (2017) refer to mother tongue instruction as accessing the curriculum through minority languages which are not officially recognised by the state. Sibanda, (2019) and Nyika (2015) provide an expanded view of mother tongue instruction as receiving education in ones' birth language or an indigenous language in which one is fluent. Oral and Lund, (2022) define it as presenting the curriculum in a local language which is compatible with the social identity of the individuals in the learning environment. Within the context of this study, mother tongue instruction is perceived to be any form of instruction which is conducted and presented in any indigenous language other than the widely adopted English language. In the case of Southern Africa and South Africa in particular, it can be instruction through any of the Nguni languages being Zulu (isiZulu), Xhosa (isiXhosa), Swazi (isiSwazi) and Ndebele

(isiNdebele), Sotho languages which comprise Northern Sotho (Sepedi), Tswana (Setswana), and Southern Sotho (Sesotho) languages, Shangaan-Tsonga (Xitsonga), and Venda (Tshivenda). Mother tongue instruction is further regarded to be the presentation of the curriculum using indigenous and Afrocentric epistemologies, ontologies, pedagogies, and tools which acknowledge the local contexts of students. It is conducting teaching and learning in one's first language.

The concept of decolonisation epistemologies in higher education has received a lot of research attention over the last decade (Hungwe & Ndofirepi, 2022; Letsekha, 2022; Mdzanga & Moeng, 2021; Merisi et al., 2022; Ndlovu-Gatsheni, 2021; R'boul, 2022; Timmiset al., 2022). At the core of decolonisation epistemologies is the call for transformation of higher education with particular emphasis on mother tongue instruction across the curriculum. To this end, research and ongoing discourses on decolonization epistemologies demonstrate compelling consensus on its meaning and implications in education. Letsekha (2022) argues that decolonisation epistemologies call for an education and a curriculum which is Afrocentric, and which prioritises African discourses.

Dawson (2020) and R'boul, (2022) concur with the earlier views of Mbembe, (2016) that decolonisation epistemologies argue that African epistemologies and ontologies should be recognised in higher education and occupy the same space with Western and Eurocentric epistemologies and ontologies. Subscribing to this school of thought, Letsekha (2022) supports the views of Mahabeer (2020) who submits that decolonisation epistemologies are entrenched in the idea that higher education should undergo radical transformation to acknowledge and recognise indigenous epistemologies as valuable tools in the creation and acquisition of knowledge. Indigenous languages are part of these tools that constitute indigenous epistemologies. Letsekha, (2022) further argues that decolonisation epistemologies are grounded in the assumption that processes related to the aim and nature of education need to be seriously revised to provide for the marginalised and neglected. Included in this provision for the marginalised and neglected is legitimizing and recognizing indigenous languages in curriculum implementation.

Given the historical context and injustices that define the South African higher education landscape, Lumadi (2021) argues that the current dispensation in higher education continues to promote and perpetuate social injustice and inequality. This claim is interpreted to also include accounting education as one of the disciplines that is still characterized by issues of social injustice. With social injustice and language inequality being a distinctive characteristic in most higher education systems which continue to favor Western and

Eurocentric epistemologies and ontologies, the discourse on decolonization epistemologies has gained momentum and popularity in academic spaces. (Dawson, 2020; Horsthemke, 2017; Jansen, 2017; Jogee et al., 2018; Leibowitz, 2017; Letsekha, 2022; Mahabeer, 2020; Manathunga et al., 2021; Mbembe, 2016; Mdzanga & Moeng, 2021; R'boul, 2022).

Rooted in these decolonisation epistemologies is the call for mother tongue instruction in all learning areas, including accounting education (Letsekha, 2022; Nyika, 2015; Qi et al., 2021; Sibanda, 2019). While this is already a very popular discourse in education, studies on the feasibility and practicability of mother tongue instruction remain very scarce, let alone in accounting education. In South Africa, Sibanda (2019) cautions that while mother tongue instruction is a fundamental human right, just like in other countries across the globe, its implementation is problematic and complicated since it is not compatible with the language repertoires of students. Similar challenges have been experienced in other countries like Sweden, Australia and Denmark (Ganuza & Hedman, 2017; Oral & Lund, 2022) and Tanzania (Nyika, 2015). Oral and Lund, (2022) and Sibanda (2019) attribute this complexity to the multilingual context of the learning environment. The above line of thought is also endorsed by Krause (2018) who points out that the serious misconceptions often made when calling for mother tongue instruction is assuming that all learning contexts are homogeneous while this is not the case in reality.

Oral and Lund, (2022), Ganuza and Hedman (2017), Sibanda (2019) and Nyika (2015) concur that the multiple language composition which defines most student constituencies complicate the implementation of mother tongue instruction; hence, the ongoing contestations and challenges. This study subscribes to this submission and argues that in the context of a diverse student-driven 21st century learning environment and the concept of a global village, mother tongue instruction will continue to be a very contested yet important phenomenon. The position taken by this study in this is in line with the earlier views of Foley (2007) who observed that the standard forms of written African languages was outdated, contextualised, narrow, and not consistent with the modern scientific world. For Foley (2007), African languages are only useful for communication at interpersonal conversation levels. Agreeing with this argument, Matentjie (2010) maintains that in their current standard written form, African languages have not yet been advanced enough for effective academic and scholarly discourses to serve as well-established languages of instruction in education. These concerns have also been raised and confirmed in this study.

In fact, Sibanda (2019) indicates that the major African languages in South Africa do not have adequate literature to enhance and promote effective

teaching and learning. In support of this assertion, Cook (2013) maintains that there are cases where educators were forced to develop their own reading content for comprehension activities. Supporting this line of thought, Nyika (2015) argues that not all teachers can converse effectively with learners in a given second language. Considering the above submissions, Sibanda (2019) views mother tongue instruction as a limiting factor on the academic progress of learners in the early years of their education, especially in disadvantaged schools. On the contrary, mother tongue instruction is viewed to benefit learners in more affluent schools whose first language is English and Afrikaans. Commenting on learners' poor academic performance in many instances, Sibanda (2019) argues that the major contributing factor is presenting the curriculum in a second language.

Nevertheless, the rationale for mother tongue instruction is expressed in the sentiments of Qi et al. (2021) who argue that the scarcity of doctoral degrees conducted in an indigenous language is a matter of serious concern, which calls for radical transformation in higher education. Qi et al. (2021) further point to the unavailability of supervisors and support staff who can assist in an indigenous language as an indicator of lack of transformation in higher education, especially when it comes to language issues. Moreover, the current calls for mother tongue instruction across the curriculum have thus far not advocated for a specific language that should be promoted but have rather called for a blanket approach which recognises indigenous tools and Afrocentric epistemologies and ontologies (Dawson 2020; Lumadi, 2021; Manathunga et al., 2021). It is in this context that this study looked at the feasibility, sustainability, and practicability of mother tongue instruction from a general and broad specific, making provision for designated ethnic groups to further interrogate this call within their own immediate circumstances. This has also informed the discussion of the study findings, which was not based on a specific language, but rather in terms of mother tongue instruction in general as a broad phenomenon.

The position taken by the researcher on the phenomena under investigation is that with adequate preparations at grassroot level, which is 'Early Childhood Development', and scientific supporting data, mother tongue instruction can be very effective in reducing social inequality and language inequality in higher education. Following the same line of thought, Lumadi (2021) observes that to promote social cohesion, enhance inclusivity, advance multilingualism, meaningful and purposeful participation of all students, there have been language policy reforms specifically focusing on the historically marginalized (Letsekha, 2022; Mahabeer, 2020). Despite these efforts and pronouncements, Lumadi (2021) laments that the very same curriculum in higher education still perpetuates serious inequalities. To support this claim, reference can be made to the collective observations of Mdzanga and Moeng, (2021) and Leibowitz

(2017), who found that the majority of students in higher education access the curriculum in academic arrangements that do not reflect their social identities.

Supporting the above sentiments and observations, Majee and Ress (2020) suggest that efforts to decolonise the curriculum and higher education in countries such as South Africa and Brazil have neither been smooth nor linear. To this effect, R'boul (2022) endorses the findings of Mdzanga and Moeng (2021) that decolonisation efforts have been plagued with several systemic context-based challenges that have complicated the realisation of a decolonised education in many countries. Deliberating on the reluctance to implement transformation policies in higher education, Mdzanga and Moeng (2021) argue that the language factor is one of the major issues of social justice that have received a lot of attention in educational literature which still needs to see its day of implementation.

Domínguez (2019) points out that despite the commitment to social justice and equity, most education systems still struggle to provide culturally responsive pedagogies and equal learning opportunities, especially to the historically marginalised communities. Concurring with the above, Manthalu and Waghid (2019) argue that there are serious challenges to be overcome before the realisation of an education which is democratic and decolonised. However, Le Grange (2016) shares different views from those expressed by Mdzanga and Moeng (2021), Domínguez, (2019) and Lumadi (2021) on the implementation of transformation policies in the higher education landscape. As such, Le Grange (2016) maintains that there have been some serious efforts in the higher education system to transform the ontological and epistemological issues that have been neglected in pedagogical practice and curriculum design.

Considering the main themes emerging from the discourses on transformation in higher education (Leibowitz, 2017; Letsekha, 2022; Lumadi, 2021), it is conceivable to conclude that the observations of Le Grange (2016) do not apply to a wider higher education system. With all the complexities and dynamics in which language is embedded in as an instrument to advance social justice and social transformation, Letsekha (2022) and Mdzanga and Moeng (2021) collectively submit that there has not been any paradigm shift when it comes to language policies in higher education in the current educational dispensation. Mahabeer (2020) advances that while the idea of decolonising the curriculum in higher education is well pronounced, curriculum transformation which should take place at all levels of education has not yet been achieved.

Lumadi (2021) and Mahabeer (2020) ratify the earlier submission of Vygotsky (1978) that students come to the learning environment with a wide range of linguistic resources which they use and apply in their daily lives to construct meaning and sense out their experiences. Vygotsky (1978) emphasizes the

importance of the learning environment to provide for these linguistic resources for students to experience learning which is not only relevant to them, but experiences which make learning meaningful and purposeful as well. Regrettably, Merisi et al. (2022), Letsekha (2022) and Timmis et al. (2022) lament that, currently, the institutions of higher learning do not recognise these linguistic resources and tools as legitimate practice. Qi et al. (2021) support this argument by adding that indigenous languages and traditional approaches to the production of knowledge have been historically excluded and belittled. Qi et al. (2021) proceed to argue that these are significant epistemological resources for research and provide a strong rationale to advocate for the use of indigenous languages as part of decolonising the curriculum. Building on these debates, the use of mother tongue instruction to promote social justice and language equity in accounting education becomes a very appealing and justified call.

Mdzanga and Moeng (2021) concur with Chandanabhumma and Narasimhan (2020) that so much theoretical arguments have been advanced and presented on how language remains uncontestably a means of demonstrating, expressing, and exercising power, authority, social class, privilege and racial superiority in various contexts. For instance, when exploring the hegemonic officially adopted languages of teaching and learning within the context of the South African higher education landscape, Afrikaans and English still represent white dominancy, supremacy, and privilege. In Australia, Qi et al. (2021) also argue that white supremacy is still very prevalent in higher education and finds expression in the extensive use of English in many programmes. Taking a very contradictory position, R'boul (2022) argues that given the dominance of western epistemologies and English, decolonisation epistemologies can only be realised through the English language. Alluding to the above views of R'boul (2022), Liddicoat (2016) suggests that knowledge of English is considered enough for one to fully partake in the process of decolonising the curriculum and higher education. While these submissions by R'boul, (2022) and Liddicoat (2016) are valid in the context of a diverse student population, language equity implies that all languages should be regarded as equal in the learning environment while diversity, as a construct of equality demands recognition of every student's profile. This is what complicates the dialogue on mother tongue instruction and makes its implementation a conundrum for the stakeholders involved in education.

When it comes to higher education in particular and research, scholars such as Letsekha (2022), R'boul (2022), Liddicoat (2016) and Qi et al. (2021) strongly advocate for the decolonisation of research and the scholarly processes of producing knowledge by using indigenous languages to enhance social justice and equity. Consequently, Qi et al. (2021) have joined in the calls to advocate for radical transformation in higher education to respond to issues of language

and culturally diverse pedagogies and supervision. Acknowledging the dominance of Western and Eurocentric epistemologies, R'boul (2022) and Nyika (2015) concur that, globally, English remains the dominant language of instruction in many universities and institutions of higher learning. R'boul (2022) further concurs with Qi et al. (2021) that the production of knowledge, teaching and learning is still fundamentally entrenched in Western and Eurocentric ideologies.

In support of the above, Tight (2019) endorses the earlier cautions of Nyika (2015) that the excessive use of English as a preferred language of instruction and communication in higher education perpetuates issues of social injustice and language inequality. Ratifying these sentiments, Guilherme et al. (2018) posit that this also perpetuates power imbalances among those occupying these spaces. Letsekha (2022) concurs with Mbembe (2016) and Tight (2019) that this practice does not only pose a serious risk of worsening epistemic and social injustices, but it also further marginalises indigenous languages and knowledge systems by creating the assumption that English is inherently superior and important than any indigenous language. Similar concerns to this effect have also been raised by Díaz, (2018), Timmis et al. (2022), and Merisi et al. (2022) in their recent works on the phenomenon under investigation.

In South Africa, decolonisation epistemologies find expression in the founding principles of the National Curriculum Statement Grades R-12 (Department of Basic Education, 2012). As enshrined in the Curriculum and Assessment Policy Statement (CAPS) for Accounting, grades 10-12 (2015, p. 4), the two most distinguishable principles that are compatible with, and that advocate for, decolonisation epistemologies are:

Social transformation: ensuring that the educational imbalances of the past are redressed, and that equal educational opportunities are provided for all sections of the population and,

Human rights, inclusivity, environmental and social justice: infusing the principles and practices of social and environmental justice and human rights as defined in the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa. The National Curriculum Statement Grades R-12 is sensitive to issues of diversity such as poverty, inequality, race, gender, language, age, disability and other factors.

Further to the above, decolonisation epistemologies are also deeply embedded in the Bill of Rights, the ethos, and values of the South African Human Rights Commission (CHE, 2023) and the Constitution of the republic of South Africa, both of which are fundamental legislation which inform and influence the provision of basic and higher education in South Africa. Thus, as part of

decolonisation epistemologies, the call for mother tongue instruction across the curriculum is not only justifiable, but it is also a legitimate and legally compliant call which is supported by legislation.

Based on the above, the advocates of mother tongue instruction advance that legislatively and legally, everyone has a right for mother tongue instruction across the curriculum. However, the reality is that the feasibility, sustainability, and practicability of providing mother tongue instruction across the curriculum are highly contested and questionable. The calls for mother tongue instruction as part of decolonisation epistemologies seems genuine, legitimate, and well-intended; however, it poses some significant risks in reversing the gains and progress that has been made towards social cohesion. In fact, it threatens to disadvantage the marginalised further. Practically, mother tongue instruction can lead to societal disintegration and the creation of isolated communities (Liu, 2020; Nyika, 2015; Tight, 2019).

This paper argues that the implementation and realisation of mother tongue instruction can only happen in the second or third generation from the current one, after years of extensive research on its feasibility, sustainability, and practicability. The position is taken considering that the adoption and implementation of mother tongue instruction should start at grassroot level and then be sustained throughout the education system, depending on the hierarchy of the education dispensation involved (Lumadi, 2021; Mahabeer, 2020). In a South African context, this would be rolled out first in the foundation phase, proceed to the intermediate phase, senior phase and further education and training, which will usually lead to institutions of higher learning.

Against the above backdrop, this study sought to explore the perceived contribution of decolonisation epistemologies in promoting social justice and language equity in accounting education and to obtain the perceptions of accounting educators on the feasibility, sustainability, and practicability of mother tongue instruction in accounting education. To achieve this, the following overarching research questions were posed:

- How do decolonisation epistemologies contribute towards promoting social justice and language equity in accounting education?
- What are the perceptions of accounting educators on the feasibility, sustainability, and practicability of mother tongue instruction in accounting education?

3. Method

To be consistent with its aim, the study employed a qualitative research approach in which a questionnaire and focus group interviews were used to

collect qualitative data from the study participants. Exploring the contribution of decolonisation epistemologies in promoting social justice and language equity in accounting education required the researcher to obtain the views of accounting educators on the phenomenon under investigation.

It is also important to underscore that while this is not always the case, exploration studies tend to be of a qualitative nature (Creswell & Poth, 2016). To satisfy the aim of the study, it was necessary to interrogate the various perceptions and perspectives of the study participants on the contribution of decolonisation epistemologies in promoting social justice and language equity in accounting education and as Bryman (2016) would recommend, this resonated very well with the qualitative approach. The selection of the qualitative research approach was also in line with the recommendations of Richards (2020), who suggests that a comprehensive and holistic exploration of a given study phenomenon requires free expression of participants' views. In this way, issues about decolonisation epistemologies in promoting social justice and language equity in accounting education were discussed in depth and comprehensively.

3.1. Participants

The researcher purposefully selected eighteen study participants with a Bachelor of Education Degree with accounting as a major specialization subject. These participants were teaching accounting in the Further Education and Training phase (FET, grades 10-12) in public schools in South Africa. It was anticipated that since they were already teaching accounting (FET), and through their phenomenological reflections on teaching the subject, they would be able to respond to the questions on decolonisation epistemologies in promoting social justice and language equity in accounting education meaningfully and effectively.

Additionally, the study participants had two or more years teaching experience of accounting (FET) and had diverse social identities, thereby being an accurate representation of the South African society. The diverse composition of the study participants also enabled the researcher to explore the contribution of decolonisation epistemologies in promoting social justice and language equity in accounting education from perspectives of the different indigenous languages in South Africa. Each participant had to imagine teaching accounting content in their own mother tongue and then respond to the questions that were posed to them.

3.2. Materials

A questionnaire with open ended questions was used to obtain qualitative data from the study participants. These questions were based on purposefully

selected issues on mother tongue instruction in accounting education and decolonization epistemologies. It was anticipated that these open-ended questions would provide the respondents with an opportunity to express themselves freely on the issues covered by those questions. Creswell and Poth, (2016) and Richards, (2020) also advocate the use of open ended questions in exploration studies of this nature. For validation purposes and as a triangulation strategy, focus group interviews were used to interrogate the findings coming from the questionnaires. For this purpose, the researcher developed questions for the focus group interviews based on the main findings from the questionnaires.

3.3. Procedure

The researcher administered the questionnaire electronically through emails. Given the different geographical positions in which the study participants were located, emailing the questionnaires to them was regarded as the most reasonable and practical way of administering the questionnaire. To avoid compromising the study participants in terms of their daily routines and putting them under pressure, they were given two days to complete the questionnaires and send them back to the researcher. This was also meant to provide them with enough time to provide well thought meaningful responses. Once all the questionnaires were received, the researcher analyzed the qualitative data using the thematic approach. The findings from the questionnaires were used to develop a set of questions which were then comprehensively deliberated on in the focus group interview sessions. The focus group interview sessions were organized and conducted online using the *Microsoft Teams* platform. As alluded to earlier, this decision was informed by the different geographical positions of the study participants. Each focus group interview session comprised six accounting educators and was one hour long, with a ten-minute break after 30 minutes. These accounting educators were randomly grouped without following any specific pattern. With the permission of the study participants, these focus group interviews were audio recorded using a recording device which was password protected.

4. Results

The presentation of results will start with the qualitative findings from the questionnaires. These results will be presented according to the main themes that emerged and stood out, making some comparisons with the focus group interview findings. As advised by Creswell and Poth (2016) and Richards (2020), the interpretation of the study findings was informed by the themes that emerged through inductive content analysis. Bryman (2016) recommends that when analysing qualitative data, it is important to classify it into themes

and sub-themes. As such, the study followed the same approach. Appendix A displays the dominant themes and the minor ones corroborating them.

5. Discussion

Responding to the first research question, on how decolonisation epistemologies contribute to promoting social justice and language equity in accounting education, this study has found that the major contribution of decolonization epistemologies to this effect is that they create awareness of issues of social justice and equity in higher education. Most importantly, decolonization epistemologies conscientize the marginalized about the importance of adopting and embracing their underrated indigenous epistemologies to deal with access, success, and equity in higher education. Being very radical in nature, decolonization epistemologies also advance that student are not spectators in the theatre of education. Instead, they should actively push the boundaries of academic and political discourse on indigenous epistemologies and ontologies (Horsthemke, 2017; Jansen, 2017; Jogie et al., 2018; Leibowitz, 2017; Mdzanga and Moeng, 2021). In their deliberations on the possible contribution of decolonization epistemologies towards promoting social justice and language equity in accounting education participant A3 commented:

Being taught in mother tongue makes one to realise that their language is not inferior. It gives them a sense of belonging and challenges them to actively participate in issues that affect them in the classroom. It awakens them to their right to be taught in their mother tongue.

Agreeing with this view, participant C5 remarked:

Using a foreign language in the classroom makes learners to regard their own language as inferior and ultimately, it reduces their confidence and sense of self-worth.

The above findings confirm the views of Nyika (2015) and R'boul (2022) who argue that recognising indigenous epistemologies and language in the learning environment—which Salmani Nodoushan (2023) has referred to as a 'petri dish' or a 'panopticon'—is the first step in promoting social justice and language equity. Lumadi (2021) and Qi et al. (2021) express similar verdicts when they argue that a fair and socially just learning space should acknowledge the uniqueness and diversity of students.

Another important finding on the possible contribution of decolonization epistemologies towards promoting social justice and language equity in education is their advocacy for policy reforms and transformation in higher

education. In advocating for a decolonised higher education, decolonisation epistemologies promote diversity and inclusivity of the marginalised. Evidence in support of this prognosis comes from participant B2, who believes that:

A decolonised learning environment respects every language and culture. So every language has a similar space in such a set up. Why forcing me to engage in learning in a second language while I can do so in my own language?

The popularity of this school of thought is demonstrated by the collective views of participants C2 and C6, who agreed with participant C4 that:

To be quite frank, the real transformation of higher education should deliver the core values of diversity and inclusivity.

Consistent with this finding is the work of Qi et al. (2021) and Mdzanga and Moeng (2021) which emphasise that the practical realisation of a transformed and decolonised higher education is exemplified by unquestionable inclusivity and diversity of epistemological expositions.

Concerning the second research question on the perceptions of accounting educators on the feasibility and practicability of mother tongue instruction in accounting education, the main point is that educators are very doubtful and not convinced. The findings reflect a picture of doubt, caution, and optimism. The accounting educators appreciate and support the call for mother tongue instruction in accounting education. However, one of the major and compelling findings emerging from their perceptions is that mother tongue instruction is not feasible and sustainable now. This confirms the views of Sibanda (2019) and Nyika (2015). In this study, this finds expression in the voices of participant A5 who said:

I really can't imagine teaching the accounting equation and financial statements in Setswana. For me, this is a mission impossible, but a genuine call.

The above sentiments support the findings of Mahabeer (2020) in a qualitative and interpretive study which explored black women's perceptions of decolonising the curriculum within a very dynamic and ever changing South African school context. Alluding to the views of A5 above, participant B6 had this to say:

Colleagues, I am not sure if this will happen in this life, but whenever it happens, it will definitely lead to more social disintegration and isolated communities. When this happens, we will need to have an educator for

every language, an employer, a church and political party for every ethnic group. I am very fearful.

Further evidence corroborating the analysis above comes from participant C3 who argued that:

An inclusive classroom should acknowledge all the languages of learners in the classroom. But I just can't imagine how every indigenous language will have its own class. It is simply too theoretical for me.

In another session, participant B4 made this submission:

Whenever it happens, it is going to be time consuming explaining simple Accounting concepts in very long and complex indigenous languages. The translation really needs to be on point. Imagine the New Era accounting textbook being published in vernacular. Some things are simply too theoretical and not realistic.

The above sentiments suggest that the South African education system is underprepared and resourced for mother tongue instruction and that the South African economy, political, social, and religious spaces are also not ready to serve and provide equal opportunities for graduates of mother tongue instruction. Amid the concerns raised in the perceptions above, the participants also embraced the idea of mother tongue instruction as a positive development which can instill a sense of equality and promote social justice. This finding is consistent with the views of scholars such as R'boul (2022), Letsekha (2022), Zembylas (2018), and Manthalu and Waghid (2019), who argue that decolonisation epistemologies such as the recognition of indigenous languages advocate for social justice and language equity in higher education.

The views of participant A2 can be referred to this effect:

Decolonising the curriculum using indigenous languages definitely highlights the fact that no language is more important than the other languages.

Subscribing to the above comment was A1 who explained that:

It will put all the languages at the same level, including the marginalised minority ones. But, I am concerned about its sustainability and practicability.

Adding to that was A6 who said:

In all fairness, I think mother tongue instruction as part of decolonisation epistemologies promises to foster inclusivity and diversity in the schools and in higher education.

The perceptions above also endorse the views of Mdzanga and Moeng (2021) who recommend the humanisation of pedagogy as a framework and lens to comprehend language as an integral issue of social justice. To this effect, it is necessary to give African languages the necessary pedagogical value they have in education by adopting a decolonial pedagogy.

Based on the above findings, there is a consensus that the curriculum can be presented using mother tongue instruction to promote social justice and language equity in the curriculum. However, it does not prepare students for employment in a global labour market and for life in a global village. It marginalises students from significant global discourses that can shape their lives. For instance, most researchers across the globe present and communicate their findings and scholarly work in a common universal language which is understood by all the global citizens. The study further argues that by default, exposing students to completely mother tongue instruction across the curriculum alone implies that upon completion of their studies, they will be exposed to a labour market, an economy and a world which complements and conforms to their mother tongue. The probability of this happening is very slim.

Further to the above submission, the ultimate purpose of any educational system is to produce graduates who can meaningfully participate in a global society and contribute towards the betterment of those societies. Therefore, calls for mother tongue instruction across the curriculum are misinformed. The reality of mother tongue instruction is that educational systems, labour markets, economic systems, and the world itself will have to undergo radical transformation and complete revolution if they are to accommodate graduates of mother tongue instruction. If not implemented on an informed scientific basis, mother tongue instruction is likely to result in the social, economic, religious, and political marginalization based on ethnicity and language identity (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2021a). In a South African perspective, this may reverse the various types of gains that have been delivered by an education system whose curriculum has been revised several times to promote social justice, language equity, inclusivity, and diversity. Adding to this concern, the practicability and feasibility of mother tongue instruction still need to be tested on a wider scale before it can be implemented.

6. Conclusion

This paper explored the contribution of decolonisation epistemologies to promoting social justice and language equity and the views of accounting educators on the feasibility, sustainability, and practicability of mother tongue instruction in accounting education. The study has found that the adoption of mother tongue instruction is one of the few strategies for institutions of higher learning to claim inclusivity and diversity. However, its feasibility, sustainability and practicability still need to be tested and confirmed with scientific evidence. The findings of this study pave way for all stakeholders involved in education to break away from a culture of sensationalizing, emotionalizing, and politicizing fundamental discourses on decolonization of the curriculum based on theory and historical injustices. As it stands, there is no readily available conclusive scientific evidence to advocate mother tongue instruction in accounting education. The study has not found any empirical evidence from comparative studies to argue that mother tongue instruction across the curriculum is feasible, sustainable, and practical in this era.

Therefore, considering the inextricably intertwined 21st century global village, it is necessary to invest in pilot projects at grassroot level to explore the feasibility, sustainability, and practicability of mother tongue instruction. To this effect, the study calls for sober minds and extensive consultations when engaging in discourses on decolonisation epistemologies and mother tongue instruction.

A completely 'negative washback', à la Salmani Nodoushan (2021b), of a hurried implementation of the ideologies underpinning decolonisation epistemologies and mother tongue instruction without proper consultation is that it will have some undesirable effects with far reaching ramifications and implications on some of the collective and shared global agendas, such as the Palmer (2015) as pronounced by the United Nations and the global education systems. In specific, goal number 4, which pronounces on ensuring inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all and goal number 10 which talks about reducing inequality within and among countries specifically are threatened by such radical call.

Notes:

1. For more on translanguaging and other relevant topics including diversity, equity, multilingualism, decolonisation epistemologies, social justice, activism, and so forth, please see works by Balosa (2024), Chaka (2024), Hannaford and Alexander (2024), Huang (2024). Kruger-Marias (2024), Motaung (2024), Ndlangamandla (2024), Ndlangamandla et al. (2024), Nkhi and Shange (2024), Xu and Fang (2024).

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Appendix A: The themes and the sub-themes corroborating them

MAIN THEME (MAIN VIEW)	SUB THEMES/ SUPPORTING VIEWS
1. Theoretically, mother tongue instruction can benefit students whose command of English as a language of instruction is poor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students experience enhanced and better understanding when taught in mother tongue • Students can easily create meaning using mother tongue • Students can easily make some imaginations and suppositions. • Students can easily remember content taught and learned in mother tongue
2. Mother tongue instruction in accounting education is practically impossible at the moment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No qualified educators to teach accounting using indigenous languages • No textbooks in indigenous languages on Accounting • Some concepts and terms in Accounting can only be well explained in English • It is a challenge to have employment for every designated ethnic group • Educators cannot imagine an Accounting learning environment which flourishes on indigenous languages • Translation challenges
3. Mother tongue instruction across the curriculum will lead to further divisions in schools and communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A class for every indigenous language • Students may group each other according to their languages
4. Mother tongue instruction is inconsistent with the ideologies of social cohesion and the concept of a global village	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Graduates of mother tongue instruction are only limited to communities which speak that specific indigenous language • Graduates of mother tongue instruction cannot compete for opportunities outside their ethnic groups
5. Accessing the curriculum in indigenous languages is the realization of equality and diversity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mother tongue instruction points to equality in the learning environment • Mother tongue instruction points that no language is neither superior nor inferior • Mother tongue instruction instills a sense of acknowledgment and belonging, especially among the traditionally marginalized social groups